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Exploring Social Work Interventions for flood-affected vulnerable populations in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

The vulnerable populations comprising of women, the elderly, persons living with disability, and children residing in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria have suffered various devastating effects from flooding. This study explored social work interventions for the vulnerable population residing in flood-prone areas in Yenagoa during flooding to mitigate the impact while promoting their well-being. The study adopted a qualitative research design; data were elicited through in-depth interviews (IDIs) with stakeholders such as community leaders, women leaders, parents of affected children, and persons with disabilities. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data retrieved. The study adopted the Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) as a theoretical framework. Findings revealed that flooding in Bayelsa State affects the vulnerable populations residing in Yenagoa, leaving them traumatized as they suffer various degrees of losses and social issues. The findings highlight the critical issues surrounding the well-being of vulnerable victim's populations as some of them are internally displaced and rendered homeless by flooding. These individuals are compelled to seek refuge in uncompleted buildings, schools, and camps where they experience a range of social challenges such as sexual abuse, substance abuse, aggravations, disputes and even deprivation of palliatives meant for them. The study recommends that social work intervention is imperative as it contributes significantly in crisis intervention, offer psychosocial support, strategic advocacy and collaborations to mitigating the sufferings of the vulnerable groups affected by flood, while empowering their coping ability.

Keywords: Social Work, Interventions, Flooding, Vulnerable Population, Yenagoa,

INTRODUCTION

Many countries across the globe are grappling with different forms of natural disasters that have often disrupted economic and social activities, impeded developmental efforts and adversely affected people's well-being. The world leaders in a United Nation's Climate Change Conference held in Dubai, in 2023, deliberated on the great danger that global warming, and flood constitute (United Nation, 2023). Flood endangers human lives and their source of living, predisposing them to different degrees of social issues (IPCC, 2022). Historically, flooding is a major disaster in Nigeria, and has been on the increase with devastating impacts on the nation for over a period of years now. The geographical areas along the river Niger and Benue are prone to flooding (Olayinka, 2023). In 2022, a total of thirty-four (34) out of thirty-six (36) states in Nigeria experienced severe flooding, affecting approximately 3.2 million people, with 1.4 million people forcibly displaced from their homes and tragically resulting in the loss of 612 lives. It is estimated that 60% of the people drastically affected were children (UNICEF, 2022). This periodic

flooding, apart from heavy rainfalls, results from the release of water from the dams which are constructed for several purposes such as water reservoir, flood control, hydro power, irrigation, fisheries, among others. Most of the dams in Nigeria are primarily built for hydro power generation, with notable examples being the Kainji, Shiroro, and Zungeru dams. The dam is designed and constructed with a reservoir storage capacity. The hydropower dams are expected to have full capacity of water at all times in order to generate electricity. This is different from other forms of dams that are required to have storage space as buffers for flood control. Nevertheless, when a dam reaches its maximum storage capacity, it becomes crucial to release water downstream to prevent potential damage or overflows (Olayinka, 2023). Nigeria is yet to construct a dam that is mainly dedicated to flood control. Consequently, when Cameroon releases water from its Lagdo dam, it overflows to River Niger and Benue, affecting the surroundings and causing severe damage to the lives and properties of those in the affected areas.

Bayelsa State has been categorized by the Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMet) as a high-risk flood-prone area (Tonye-Scent & Uzobo, 2020; Ejike, 2022). The region, particularly around the riverine areas, experiences intensified and annual flooding due to climate change. This natural phenomenon significantly disrupts the livelihoods and activities of people within the area, while displacing thousands from their ancestral homes and residences (Michael, 2024). This climate change and environmental factors, with the existing socio-economic problems, increase the vulnerability of the populations, exacerbating the humanitarian crisis, particularly among the vulnerable groups, thereby necessitating robust and culturally sensitive social work intervention.

Statement of the Problem

Flooding occurs without warning, taking communities and individuals off guard and leaving them vulnerable to devastating consequences. This disrupts the individuals, families, and communities social functioning as victims are left to count their losses, while some slowly slip into depression, trauma, and disorder (Matlakala et al., 2022). Bayelsa State has a projected population of about 2.70 million people and spans a land area of 10773 km², it annually experiences a surge in sea and water level making communities in Yenagoa and other parts of the State to be susceptible to flooding, and displacement with members experiencing severe hardship (Michael, 2024). This environmental challenge is sometimes disastrous leading to the shutdown of the academic, and business activities in the area, leaving some members to recount their significant losses, damages of their properties, loss of lives and spread of diseases, making social work intervention necessary to address the needs of the people.

Flood victims are vulnerable, devastated, disheartened and traumatized by this natural disaster as they count their losses. Social work profession plays significant role in disaster management (Ogbanga, 2021) and facilitates the provision of services and supports that mitigates the impact of the flood, while enhancing their adaptive and coping skills (Ekwesaranna & Eze, 2021). Government, non-governmental agencies and goodwill individuals provide palliatives and various forms of support to alleviate the physical suffering, emotional pain, social and economic losses of the people. Surprisingly, some of these resources and relief materials hardly get to the victims (Chinagorom, 2023). This study explored social work intervention strategies among the vulnerable population; however, it specifically addressed how social workers address the complex needs of the vulnerable populations, bearing in mind social work theories and principles.

The annual floods in Bayelsa State, particularly in Yenagoa, have created a complex humanitarian crisis as it heightened the vulnerability of women, children, the elderly and persons with disability populations, thereby posing significant challenges for effective social work intervention (Akintoye et al., 2016; Elum & Snijder, 2023). This study was guided by following research questions:

- What are the experiences of the vulnerable populations during flooding in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?
- What social work interventions would address the psychosocial, economic, and health needs of the vulnerable populations in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Flooding occurs when the land is covered and submerged by water. It is the inundation of dry areas as a result of an increase in the level of water, such as rivers, lakes, dams, streams, and canals (Agbonkhese et al., 2014; Ogbanga, 2021). Families are left traumatized as breadwinners; children or other family members are swept off to untimely death by flood (Adeola, 2022). Flooding affects the infrastructure, health, psychology, and socio-economic wellbeing of victims in a manner that is unprecedented. This disaster poses an environment challenge that displaces people from their homes, makes it difficult for people to access clean drinking water among other unique social issues (Besthorn & Meyer, 2019). Social work profession plays significant role in disaster management, as they are committed in assisting and supporting affected persons, families and communities affected by the natural disasters (Amadasun, 2020; Shokane, 2019). They collaborate and partner with governmental, non-governmental and private agencies to address the needs and provide comprehensive care continuum to affected persons (Shokane, 2019). This intervention is imperative as flooding has mental, social, and health effects on victims (Othman et al., 2022).

Studies revealed that Yenagoa, and by extension Bayelsa State, and other States in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria had suffered devastating effects of flooding since 2012 which caused colossal damages to the lives and social heritage of the people within the region (Amede & Ejumudo, 2021; Arausi et al., 2025). This ecological disaster over time has gradually become an annual menace and treat with devastating effects particularly on the vulnerable populations that include: children, the aged, and people with disabilities among others (Akintoye et al., 2016). Social work is a profession that helps people coping abilities globally. They intervene during disasters and national emergencies, as they play significant roles in disaster management. However, there is a notable gap of literatures and documentation of social work interventions among flood affected vulnerable populations in Yenagoa.

Studies on social work intervention in disaster management, particularly on intervention among vulnerable groups, are quite limited. This Keketso et al. (2021) in their study believes is a major challenge, in packaging a programmes and interventions that targets the needs of vulnerable groups. In their view also, inadequate resources, insufficient training and lack of collaboration with agencies on humanitarian and natural disaster makes it difficult for the vulnerable populations to be adequately cared for. Udokporo et.al. (2025), in their study observed that poor flood risk management strategies contribute to the neglect of the vulnerable populations as this makes it difficult for them to access or benefit from relief materials provided for them. They are of the view that flood reductions strategies and management policies are yet to impact the vulnerable population in Nigeria. For Amadasun (2020), the remedial approach in service delivery to the vulnerable population particularly the internally displaced persons emphasize the need for paradigm shift in interventions for the vulnerable populations. There is need for all stakeholders involved to harness a more robust approach in their interventions, incorporating a more proactive measures, with ecological, environmental and strategic social approaches (Shokane, 2019).

Since 2012, Bayelsa State among other States along the Niger Delta Region, have experienced devastating flooding in some communities, which has driven residents out of their homes, with negative impact disrupting their socio-cultural lives and heritage (Amede & Ejumudo, 2021; Arausi, et al., 2025). This ecological challenge predisposes a good number of vulnerable groups to live threatening situations that disrupt their well-being. The annual flooding contributes significantly to emotional stress and psychological problems (Mfon, 2024; Mzinyane, et. al., 2024). Despite the interdisciplinary collaborations in managing disasters, there are inadequate references on social work interventions particularly among vulnerable groups. This study aims at highlighting the need for social work interventions and response especially in disaster management particularly among vulnerable populations in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The study also made recommendation for further research.

Theoretical Review

Theoretically, this study is based on the Disaster Risk and Reduction (DRR) model of Lena Dominelli in 2012. This study presents empirical validation that flooding is a disaster that forcefully displaces residents including land owners and landlords, rendering them homeless, jobless, destroying properties worth

millions of naira. This disaster distorts economic growth, affects the physical, social, mental, and health wellbeing of the residents particularly the vulnerable populations who are forcefully displaced by the flood, predisposing them to different forms of physical and psychological risks. This situation explains their actions and inactions on prevention strategies and the need to prepare for flood disaster. Using this model, emphasis is placed on understanding the predicaments of these vulnerable populations, addressing their needs and challenges through strategic interventions such as community assessment and mapping, which would not just identify flood prone areas, but, ensure that vulnerable victims are catered for, including their well-being even after the floods (Ikeorji; Akah, & Ramsey-Soroghaye, 2024).

Bearing this in mind, social workers participate actively in building community readiness through sensitization programmes and workshops, collaborate with the media agencies in educating the populace with adequate information on the impending dangers of the flood, safety tips and strategies. Apart from providing psychosocial support, social workers explore structural, environmental and political factors that predisposes the vulnerable populations to dangers. Among other challenges, the mobility of vulnerable victims are incapacitated, their health is compromised, making it difficult for them to seek help and safety timely by themselves (Oru Tiku et.al. 2025) as the sudden and unexpected nature of the flood predisposes victims to trauma, pain and grief, hence social intervention becomes imperative.

This model provides a framework for the proper resettling of the displaced vulnerable populations, by the government through policies, adequate planning and interventions. Also, it is important to mobilize and engage the community and relevant stakeholders in mitigating the devastating effect of flooding among the vulnerable groups (Michael, 2021; Ejike, Dossen, & Ikenna, (2022). This would guide the development of social actions, programmes, and interventions that are developed from well informed perspective, with adequate knowledge of the dilemma experienced by these vulnerable populations. Additionally, technology and different social media platforms can be harnessed for adequate communication, dissemination of information, community and resource mobilization as well as distribution (Smith & Davis 2021).

The model recommends that the lives of residents can be improved in order to mitigate the drastic effect and risk they experience through strategic planning and adequate funding. Consequently, social workers must be incorporated and collaborate with government and non-governmental agencies in providing services for vulnerable populations affected by floods, as apart from providing palliatives to them, sustainable measures and solutions are to be put in place to mitigate the negative impact of flooding, particularly among the vulnerable in the State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This qualitative research study examined the experiences and dilemmas of vulnerable populations of flood victims residing in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa State, and the responses of social work in mitigating the impact of the flood. Within Bayelsa State, Igbogene, Akenfa, Azikoro, Yenagoa main town, and Ovom were purposively selected as case study areas because they have consistently been highly impacted by the flood and forced displacement of the residents. The Epie Creek and Ekole River overflow to these areas through natural creeklets and canals, which empty into Epie Creek. Yenagoa is a heterogeneous city, comprising of people from different geographical areas, from different walks of life, who have come to the city in search of greener pastures.

The purposive sampling technique was used to select twenty (20) households across five areas that have perpetually been flooded. Quota sampling, a non-probability sampling method, was used to determine the proportion of families that have always been forcibly displaced by floods in the selected area. They include: Igbogene (3), Akenfa (4), Azikoro (5), Yenagoa main town (5) and Ovom (3). An in-depth interview was the primary instrument used to elicit data from the participants. The data was collected in the setting of the participants, reflecting their experiences and realities. The in-depth interview was structured in sections reflecting the objective of the study and arranged in themes and sub-themes which focused on specific topics and ideas. The interview and discussions lasted between 45 minutes to 1 hour. The respondents voluntarily participated.

Ethical considerations were considered in conducting the research with the vulnerable populations resident in the study area, particularly in respect to informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity of participants were spelt out. Psychological support was provided to ensure the well-being of participants. The data elicited from the study were analyzed using thematic analysis as the responses of participants were articulated and presented. The thematic content analysis was carried out using three different approaches: firstly, the research tool determined certain concepts; secondly, informal conversations were coded; and thirdly, outcomes were categorized into themes. Conventionally, the data were coded; themes were derived directly as relevant to the study. A summary of the content analysis was used to generate valuable information on areas of comparison and interpretation of important content through the experiences of the participants.

RESULTS

In this section, the data elicited from the study are presented, analyzed, and interpreted. They are categorized into the participant's background information and the objectives of the study. The study involved twenty (20) families. These families were represented by their respective heads.

Participant's background information

The participants from Igbogene constitute 15% of the sample, 20% were drawn from Akenfa, 25% from Azikoro Town, 25% from Yenegoa Town, 15% from Ovom. With regard to gender, the majority (55%) of the participants were male, while 45% were female. The average age of the participants was 44 years. Regarding the occupation of the participants, 55% of them were civil servants, while 25% were traders and in business, 15% were artisans, and 5% were farmers.

Theme 1: General Experience of Residents

Findings from the study revealed that all of the participants had experienced flooding. The participants stated that flooding is now a recurring perennial issue which practically shuts down everything and makes it difficult for the residents to live their normal life. Others further stated that whenever flood is predicted, residents are not aware of the enormity of the water. For instance, one of the participants noted thus:

Prior to the time we slept; the compound was dry with no trace of water around. Only for us to wake up to find the whole compound flooded. The water did not emanate from heavy rains as there has been no rain for the past one week. I learnt the flood was from the release of water from the Lagdo dam. The speed at which the flood rises and spreads is unprecedented. In two days, the water has passed the knee level of a tall adult. By the third day, we were forced to build racks to raise some of our properties as the level of the water became unbearable. The roof ceiling was also used to keep some properties before we were forced to leave the compound. The roads became impassable, particularly for small and saloon cars, as some parts of the road were cut off and destroyed (Male IDI participant/Civil servant/ Aged 47 years).

With reference to the above statement, one can perceive the pain, agony and dilemma of the interviewee due to flooding. This disaster, the interviewee noted leaves him and his household with unsatisfactory alternatives and a wide range of physical, social, economic, health and psychological challenges. The interview also reflects on the concern about the wellbeing of the residents during flooding, particularly as majority of the residents are forced out of their homes by the flood. Another of the interviewee who is also affected by the flood noted:

My family was forced to take refuge in the Internally Displaced People's (IDP) camp at Oxbow Lake. I had no privacy. Hundreds of people had to share the camp. Some rooms had no windows as we had to use wrappers and materials to cover the windows. Despite that, the mosquitoes were much, the toilets and bathrooms were grossly inadequate. The numbers of people in the camp were more than the facilities available. I had to wake up very early to take my bath sometimes outside. It was also difficult to eat well as the food provided was rationed and difficult to come by. We had to line up in queues for a long time before portion of food gets to us. There was inadequate good and clean drinking water. The cost of items like pure water skyrocketed ranging

from #300 to #500 a bag. This was beyond the reach of many. The entire environment was not conducive at all (Female IDI participant/Artisan/Aged 36 years).

The above interview response shows that the welfare of the residents was unsatisfactory during flooding seasons, particularly regarding their health and general wellbeing. This predisposed the residents to several health and social problems such as malaria, cold, skin infection, and sexual abuse among others (Oru Tiku et.al. 2025). One of the participants also noted that:

Young people in particular were vulnerable to sexual abuse and molestation as a young man in his early twenties was caught molesting a younger male teenager sexually. One may wonder how many people had been victim to this abuse before it came to lime light (Male IDI participant/Businessman/Aged 45 years).

The view of this interviewee was affirmed by the report of Daily Trust (Sunday, 6th November 2022), which stated that the operatives of the Bayelsa State anti-kidnapping squad arrested and paraded a group of young teenagers that were between 14 to 16 years old in an Internally Displaced Camp (IDP) that engaged in the act of buggery every night, at the water side. This incidence was also confirmed by the Oxbow Lake camp Coordinator, Hon. Koku Obiyah Ebiowo. Additionally, participants note that flooding contributes to environmental problems and this is believed to largely enable by the behavior of man. One of the participants noted that:

The inability of the State Government to follow the master plan of the State, the indiscriminate building of hotels and petrol stations on canals and natural water ways and paths, makes it difficult for the water to have a free flow when rain falls. Some of the buildings along the waterways are owned by 'big guys' and even government officials. Nobody questions or sanctions them. This has contributed to the incessant flooding experienced by residents in Yenagoa metropolis. Additionally, the inability to have a proper drainage system, for roads constructed in the metropolis has made the problem complicated, as no part of the State is spared from flood. The water stinks as people take advantage of it to dispose of waste indiscriminately (Male IDI participant/Retiree/Aged 63 years).

Drawing from these findings, these environmental problems constitute great danger to the health and wellbeing of the people. Poor sanitation, open defecation, improper disposal of waste, expose residents to diseases such as cholera, diarrheal, dysentery among other public health issues (Ogbu, 2022). A participant noted that:

The tremendous force of the flood excavated buried corpses at Azikoro government cemetery. This constituted a public health and environmental problem to residents around that area (Male IDI participant/Businessman /Aged 47 years). This view corroborates that of the chairperson of the Bayelsa flood committee, who is also the Commissioner for Environment, Iselema Gbaranbiri, who noted in a statement that decomposing corpses were found around the cemetery area (Premium Times, October 18, 2022).

The Bayelsa State government expressed her dissatisfaction on the federal government response towards the plight and dilemma of residents of Bayelsa State, particularly on the acclaimed statement of the minister of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development, that "Bayelsa is not among 10 worst hit States in 2022 flooding in Nigeria" (Oyadonngba & Agbakwuru, 2022). The Bayelsa State Emergency Management Agency (BYSEMA) in its report noted that 96 persons lost their lives, with 1.2 million persons displaced from their homes (Oyadonngba & Agbakwuru, 2022). The chairman of BYSEMA, Walamam Igrubia affirmed that three hundred communities were affected by the flood. Additionally, flooding erodes the self-determination of victims. This (Oyadonngba & Agbakwuru, 2022) affirms that as residents are forcefully evicted from their homes and are forced to stay together with other victims in IDP camps, uncompleted buildings, school buildings and tents, with unbearable restrictions. This infringes on their rights to freedom. Some of them are made to pay heavily just to secure a space to rest their heads, as they have no other place to go. One of the participants noted that:

People suffer food insecurity as the flood takes over their farmlands. The flood water flushed out the fishes from the fish farms and birds from poultry farms of the people. This culminated to high

cost of living and decrease in the standard of living. A participant noted that a custard of ‘garri’ that was sold at #700 rose to #2000, while a bag of sachet water that was sold at #150 increased to #500 (Female IDI participant/Civil servant/Aged 53 years).

Another participant expressed the following views:

This disaster can sometimes be manmade, which cannot always be averted but can be well managed and handled by the government if they show commitment and exercise the right political will. Our native communities and some towns in the state have experienced this plight now and again, despite available remedies to mitigate the perennial disaster (Male IDI participant/Artisan/Aged 32years).

Theme 2: Wellbeing of Residents during Flooding

Findings revealed that families, kin members, close knits, religious organizations, community leaders, good spirited, well-meaning citizens, professional associations, government and non-governmental organizations played a significant role in ensuring that people affected by the flood were well taken care of. According to most of the participants, some of their family members were accommodated and cared for by close associates. Religious bodies also gave out food items and mosquito nets to their members during the flood. One of the participants noted:

A woman known as Ebiere Ejiro Lugbenwei, aka ‘Biere’s Catering Hub’ here in Azikoro, entered the flood water with her rain boot, cooked food, and served people freely without asking for money. She did it for a week before people started donating food items such as yams, beans, garri, rice noodles, among others, for her to cook and serve victims. Her action motivated other good-spirited citizens to assist flood victims.

Donations of foodstuffs worth 1.5 million naira were made by the Dangote Flood Committee to affected people across the nation. This was distributed through the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA). Donor agencies such as the US Agency for International Development donated funds to affected States in Nigeria (Oyadonngba & Agbakwuru, 2022). Additionally, NEMA and the Nigerian Content Development Board (NCDMB), distributed relief materials to 1000 households. The materials distributed were mainly food items, mosquito nets, bathing soap, clothing and other non-consumables (Ebiowei, 2022). This was done in collaboration with other stakeholders such as Nigerian Air Force, the Nigeria Navy through the NNS Soroh in Bayelsa State, Nigeria Red Cross, who airlifted the relief items as the roads were cut off by the flood (NEMA, 2022). Non-Governmental Organizations and Faith-Based Organizations such as South East Women Care Builders Foundation, Nigerian Christian Graduate Fellowship (NCGF), among others, donated relief items to victims. The State government made available camps to accommodate displaced residents. Nevertheless, the camps and associated facilities were grossly inadequate for the teeming populations that needed it. Access to health care services was challenging. One participant noted:

I had difficulties accessing health care services when my child took ill. This was due to the time it took for me to access a canoe from where I stay, since that was the only means of transportation to the road (Female IDI participant/Civil servant/ Aged 47 years). Similarly, a pregnant woman resident in Yenagoa Town was stranded in her apartment after successfully delivering her baby. She and the baby required urgent medical attention, and she almost lost her life. However, pregnant women in the camp had prompt medical attention. The IDP camp in Oxbow Lake welcomed a set of triplets, three sets of twins and single births. A total of twelve (12) babies were delivered in the camp during the flood period (Punch, 31 October 2022).

Theme 3: The psycho-social and economic problems associated with flooding

Findings show that the flood was traumatic for residents. This was evident as they counted their losses during the period. Most of the participants had a sour experience and story from the flood. The damages were enormous; it ranged from breaking of tiles in their houses, falling of fences, staining of the walls, spoiling of water sumo and pumps, furniture, refrigerators, clothes, mattresses, documents, books, photographs, loss of cassava farmlands, fishes in ponds, birds in poultry among others. Some also lost their close relatives. Economically, people had to spend so much to meet their basic needs. Family

members were separated from each other, thus exposing children and the elderly in particular to neglect, abuse, assault and molestation. One of the participants noted:

I had to send my children to a family member's house while I put up in a friend's place. Severally, I will call them by afternoon to know how they were faring, only to discover that they have not had a meal for the day, even after we had made provision for their feeding. Whenever I visited my children, they narrated their ordeal, which brought tears to my eyes at what they had to go through (Female IDI participant/Businesswoman/ Aged 45 years).

Another participant noted:

This flood is horrible, my family went through a lot emotionally as we had to relocate three (3) times. The flood keeps meeting up with us wherever we go (Female IDI participant/Civil servant/ Aged 50 years).

The victims (who are patriotic citizens) always count their losses and ordeals in ways that affect their livelihood and well-being. The devastating impact of the flood makes it difficult for residents and businesses within the affected areas to reside in their respective houses, homes and business places because they are forcefully displaced from their abode. Sources of livelihood were terribly affected; children were out of school as schools were also flooded and forced to close down, farmlands and products were swept off by the flood (Adeola, 2022). There is need for the Federal and State Governments to attend to this matter from the pre-flood, flood and post-flood eras.

Theme 4: The role of Social Work in flood management

Following the responses of most of the participants, a holistic multi-sectoral approach is required to drastically tackle and manage the impact of flooding in Bayelsa State. They believe that flooding in the State goes beyond government intervention alone and the provision of palliatives. Hence, there is a need to ensure a sustainable psychosocial support for residents to grapple with the effects of the flood. This entails that social workers play their role in addressing social problems and the challenges of people affected by the flood. They believe that professional social workers should be incorporated in the management team of flood disaster in Bayelsa State, deployed to provide services to residents during disasters. One of the participants noted:

I feel that social workers should be included in the team that manages disasters such as floods. Going by their training, we really need them to provide psychosocial support and counsel people as the flood drastically affects a lot of things; in fact, we find it difficult to live a normal life during and after the flood. The so-called palliative that the government provided was totally meant for those people in the IDP camps. Those of us that suffered on our own, nobody cared for us as if we were not part of flood victims. Imagine, they kept food stuff palliatives meant for victims, in the warehouse since last year, now that angry youths have looted it they claim it was spoiled. Why will food be allowed to spoil when many are hungry in the State? They would have given to us. Some persons have left Yenagoa due to the impact of this flood (Female IDI participant/Artisan/ Aged 35 years).

One of the stakeholders from the Ministry of Women, Children Affairs, Empowerment and Social Development, who is a social worker, noted:

Welfare is a major aspect of their ministry, which is made up of many social workers. Knowing the strategic role of social workers in flood management, the Nigeria Association of Social Workers (NASOW, Bayelsa Chapter) visited flood victims in Ayama Ijaw community, where we counselled flood victims and provided them with foodstuffs. These people are going through a lot, and the government alone should not be left to manage flood intervention (Male IDI /Social worker/ Aged 43 years).

Another participant also noted:

All the items such as bags of rice, bags of garri, bags of beans, cartons of noodles, toiletries, packs of bottle water among others were provided for the flood victims were from free will donations made by NASOW members in the State (Female IDI participant/Social worker/ Aged 39 years).

FINDINGS

Clearly, from the objectives of the study, it is evident that the majority of the residents in the study area were directly or indirectly affected by the flood. Those not directly affected hosted many others who were displaced by the flood. Its impact was beyond the physical as it affected the psycho-social well-being of residents. It impoverishes (Eze, Girma, Zenebe & Zenebe, 2020), and leaves victims vulnerable. This vulnerability triggers different degrees of dilemmas, several health, environmental, economic and social problems. These problems affect the effective functioning and well-being of residents in the study area, especially when unsatisfactory living conditions and challenges faced by residents during flooding seasons are considered. Consequently, it is imperative for social work profession to rise up and play significant role in addressing the myriad of emerging social problems and challenges that emanates from flooding which affects the dignity and worth of individuals, families and communities. This supports the findings of previous studies as Ogbanga (2021) which call for urgent social work response in addressing social issues that are associated with incessant flooding due to climate change.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of the study on flooding and social work response: the dilemma of Bayelsa residents, reveals a crucial emerging social issue that have persisted as a result of flooding, with devastating impact in the lives of individuals, families and communities in the State. While some residents expressed joy on the benefits of flooding in the past such as having access to alluvial soil for their farming and the different varieties of sea foods that comes with the flood, majority are now, more than ever before, left to count their losses due to the devastating effect of the flood which leaves them displaced, jobless, insecure, abused and marginalized. This study underscores the need for progressive collaboration that integrates the social work profession into the flood response programme of government and nongovernmental agencies. This will ensure a multifaceted approach in addressing the numerous physical, economic and psychosocial problems associated with flooding. Essentially, it would translate into improving the general well-being of the lives of residents particularly the vulnerable populations affected by flooding in the State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Government and other non-governmental agencies such as the Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs and the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), an interventionist agency, should identify the flood-prone areas, identify the causes of flooding and come up with sustainable mitigation measures to avoid a repeat of the perennial flooding.
- ii. Social workers should be incorporated into the development of policies and programmes for flood mitigation.
- iii. The Ecological Funds should be properly and prudently channeled to proffer lasting solution to flooding through construction of culverts, de-silting of canals, building embankments and shoreline protection amongst others.
- iv. Decent, affordable, and habitable temporary camps should be built for displaced flood victims.
- v. Adequate food and palliative should be made available to all particularly for vulnerable flood victims irrespective of their locations.

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